

Faceless Communication

A phenomenology of the absent face in digital exchange

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You send a message. The other person reads it. Both of you stand before the same words — yet neither of you sees the other. You share no face, no body, no breath, no posture. All you share is letters. This is the default mode of communication in our age: billions of messages dispatched every day without meeting face to face, without sharing a body. And most of us do not experience this as a loss — we do not even notice what has been lost.

This essay attempts to notice. What vanishes in digital communication is not merely tone of voice or facial expression. For Levinas, what vanishes is the face itself — not the physical face, but the moment when you realise the other person refuses to fit your categories, when you cannot contain them. For Merleau-Ponty, what vanishes is the body — not the body as a tool, but the body as a perceiving being: the way you sense another person's posture, tension, breath. And perhaps — if we look through Heidegger — nothing vanishes at all, because the body already goes unnoticed in everyday life, and digital communication simply makes that invisibility visible.

Three phenomenologists hold three different lenses to the same absence. This essay turns those three lenses toward digital communication and asks: when we exchange messages with someone whose face we cannot see, what do we lose, what do we gain — and what do we fail to notice?

I. Levinas: The Face and the Ethical Command

In this section, a few words work differently from their everyday meaning. Levinas's *face* is not a physical face — it is the other person's nakedness, vulnerability, their refusal to fit my definitions. *Infinity* is not mathematical — it is the fact that the other person always exceeds my grasp. And *ethical command* is not a law — it is the face's demand for responsibility simply by being there.

In 1961 Emmanuel Levinas published *Totality and Infinity*, a book that made “the face” the starting point of all ethics. But Levinas's face is not nose, eyes, mouth. The face is the other person's refusal to fit my understanding — the thing that resists being contained, possessed, defined.

Consider this: you look at someone's face. You might describe them as “angry,” “tired,” “cheerful” — but no matter how much you describe, something always remains. The person before you refuses to fit your labels. Levinas calls this refusal “infinity.” And this infinity shows itself in the face:

“The face exists by refusing to be contained. In this sense it cannot be grasped — cannot be encompassed. Neither by seeing nor by touching — because seeing and touching already convert what they grasp into content, absorbing it into our own understanding.”

— Levinas, *Totality and Infinity*, 1961, p. 194

Levinas separates the face from seeing and touching. The face is not *seen*; the face is *encountered*. Seeing is a form of capture — I define what I see, I claim it, I turn it into knowledge. But the face resists this capture. The face does not communicate information; it *imposes itself* — as the presence of someone whose existence exceeds my power.

“Thou shalt not kill”

This is Levinas's most famous formulation: to encounter the face is to receive a command. “This infinity, stronger than murder, already resists us in his face, is his face, is the primordial expression, is the first word: ‘you shall not commit murder’” (Levinas, 1961/1979, p. 199). The sentence is dense, but what it says is this: the face commands *because* it is defenceless. Nakedness, exposure, vulnerability — it is precisely this defencelessness that makes me responsible. Killing

someone is physically possible, but for anyone looking into a face, it is ethically impossible — because the face does not resist my power with force; it questions my power through its fragility.

Discourse and the Face

Levinas does not separate the face from speech; he unites them. Speech creates a bond between separate beings. But speech has two layers: what is said (information, content) and the act of speaking itself (two people standing before each other). If I focus on what is said, I reduce the other person to information. But if I open myself to the act of speaking — if I hear the person behind the words — then the other person calls me into question.

This point is critical: for Levinas, the ethical power of speech opens in the presence of the face. What, then, becomes of speech without the face?

II. Merleau-Ponty: The Body as a Perceiving Being

In his 1945 *Phenomenology of Perception*, Maurice Merleau-Ponty placed the body at the centre of philosophy. But this is not Descartes's body — a machine separate from the soul. For Merleau-Ponty, the body *is* consciousness. Thinking, feeling, perceiving — all of these happen in the body, not in some disembodied “mind.”

Directing Ourselves Toward the World Through the Body

Think of it this way: when you walk into a room, you do not first “think” about how to navigate it. Your body already knows — how to pass through the doorway, how to sit in the chair, whether you can reach the table. Merleau-Ponty calls this the body's prior acquaintance with the world: the world is “not what I think, but what I live through” (*Phenomenology of Perception*, p. 213). This living-through is accomplished through the body.

Communication works the same way. When two people talk face to face, two bodies share the same space; each senses the other's posture, tension, breathing, drawing closer and pulling away. This sensing is not deliberate — bodies read each other without thinking about it.

What Is Lost in Bodiless Communication?

From Merleau-Ponty's perspective, digital communication is a bodily rupture. Two people no longer share the same space. Neither can sense the other's posture, tension, relaxation, approach, or withdrawal. Only words remain.

But a tension arises here. Merleau-Ponty defines the body not merely as a tool but as consciousness itself. Does bodiless communication then amount to consciousnessless communication? Of course not — but it is a *different kind* of communication. The person writing continues to direct themselves toward the world through their body — touching the keyboard, looking at the screen, sitting in their chair. But this bodily experience does not *cross over* to the other person. Everyone remains in their own body, but no one can feel the other's.

This is precisely what Merleau-Ponty meant by “communication between bodies”: in face-to-face conversation, two bodies sense each other's movements, tensions, rhythms. This sensing happens without thinking about it — bodies resonate with each other, unbidden. In digital communication, this resonance drops to zero.

III. Heidegger: *The Absence of the Body*

In Martin Heidegger's *Being and Time* (1927), the body is buried in a conspicuous silence. The body barely comes up anywhere in the book. Harlaftis (2023) turns this silence into a thesis: "The body is absent and maybe rightly so."

For Heidegger, we exist in the world primarily not as a body but as an *existence*. We experience the world through the things we use — when you use a hammer, you do not notice your hand, you notice the hammer; when you walk, you do not notice your feet, you notice the path. The body, like a tool, becomes invisible as long as it works. You attend to the world, not to your body.

Harlaftis puts it this way: in our everyday experience, something called "the body" mostly does not show up at all. You do not notice your jaw while eating, your fingers while typing, your throat while speaking. The body is *absent* from our most basic experiences — because we live not *as* a body but as a being that *does things* in the world.

Is Absence a Discovery?

Harlaftis's thesis is provocative: the absence of the body is not a deficiency but the disclosure of the fundamental structure of existence. "We can interpret this absence as a possibility for a new perspective on life. We can enhance our engagement with the world," he writes.

For digital communication, this is a striking reading: the erasure of the body in text-based exchange may not be a *loss* but the *becoming-visible* of something that was already the case. In face-to-face conversation, the body is there but goes unnoticed; in messaging, the body is physically absent — but it was never really there to begin with. We are only now *noticing* the absence.

IV. Three Phenomenological Lenses, One Absence

The same phenomenon — the absence of the body and the face in digital communication — takes on three different meanings in three phenomenologists.

Levinas: Ethical Catastrophe

For Levinas, digital communication is an ethical crisis. The face was the condition of the ethical encounter — without it, I trap the other person in my own labels. In messaging, the person before me becomes “the one who is angry at me,” “the one asking for information,” “the boring one” — a category, not a person. Because I cannot see their face, nothing resists this.

Walther (1996) confirms this from a different angle: without a face, we fill the other person with our own fantasies. We see the people we like as better than they are, and the people we dislike as worse. In Levinas’s terms: I have absorbed the other person into myself; they have become my projection — their existence as a being that exceeds me, that refuses to fit my categories, has been erased.

For Levinas this is not merely a communication problem. It is the collapse of ethics. Because ethics begins with the limitation of my power — and the face is what performs that limitation. In faceless communication, power is unlimited: I can block, delete, ignore — and I feel the weight of none of it.

Merleau-Ponty: Bodily Rupture

From Merleau-Ponty’s perspective, the problem is not ethical but *perceptual*. Communication is a bodily encounter, and the digital medium splits this encounter in two. Two people cannot sense each other’s bodies. The person writing lives their own body — sitting in their chair, touching the keyboard, looking at the screen — but this experience does not reach the other side. All that remains is a thinking operation: read the words, extract the meaning, write a reply.

Heidegger: The Absence Made Visible

Heidegger’s perspective is the most provocative. The body is already absent — in everyday life, the body goes unnoticed. Digital communication makes this absence *visible*: in face-to-face conversation we forget the body is there;

in messaging we *notice* the body is not there. The difference between the two lies not in the absence itself but in whether the absence is *noticed*.

This perspective casts a research finding in new light. Gillespie-Lynch et al. (2014) found that individuals on the autism spectrum actively prefer digital communication. Through Heidegger: these individuals, who already experience the body as unnoticed, find themselves at ease when the digital medium makes that experience valid for everyone.

V. Can Discourse Carry Ethics Without a Face?

There is a tension in Levinas's thought. On the one hand, the face is the indispensable condition of the ethical encounter. On the other, Levinas grants language a privileged place: "Language establishes a relation between terms that breaks the unity of a genus... Language is perhaps to be defined as the very power to break the continuity of being or of history" (Levinas, 1961/1979, p. 195).

For Levinas, speech is not the face's instrument — it is a dimension that opens *together with* the face. To encounter someone's face is at the same time to encounter their *word*. But can this togetherness be severed?

First Reading: Sterility

Without the face, speech is reduced to a technical operation — information transfer, task coordination, social ritual. The other person's existence as a being that exceeds me does not seep into the words, because the face's resistance is missing. Blocking is a button; ignoring is an option; misunderstanding is a habit. The face's command — "thou shalt not kill" — is silent on the screen.

Second Reading: The Ethics of Speech Itself

Yet even in written words, a shattering encounter is possible — by a different path. A text exceeds its author's intention; the silence between the words can serve as a kind of "face." Literature is proof of this: we have never seen Kafka's face,

yet something breaks inside us before Gregor Samsa's transformation into a beetle — we feel a responsibility, we feel shaken.

But this analogy has limits. Literature is consciously crafted — built to compensate for the absence of the face. Everyday digital communication has no such craft. WhatsApp messages are not Kafka.

A Third Way: From Imposition to Invitation

Perhaps the question is wrongly posed. Instead of “Can faceless speech carry ethics?” we should ask: “Can the person reading a faceless message *experience* an ethical encounter?”

In a message, I *can* think of the person behind the words — their vulnerability, their need, their existence as a being that exceeds me. But this thinking is not automatic; it is a deliberate effort.

In the presence of the face, responsibility is imposed; in the digital medium, responsibility is chosen. This difference is great, but it is not absolute.

VI. Loss, Purification, and Ethics

Loss: The Ethical Dimension

The closure of the nonverbal channel is not merely a practical loss — it is an ethical one. For Levinas, the erasure of the face means the erasure of the other person's existence as a being that exceeds me. The person before me becomes a theme, a category, a profile photograph. I can contain them, define them, label them — because their face does not resist me.

This explains the deep infrastructure of online violence — trolling, hate speech, cyberbullying. In a faceless medium, hurting someone is easy because their vulnerability is invisible. On the screen there is a username, an avatar, at best a profile photo — but no face. The face's command — “thou shalt not kill” — is structurally weakened on the screen.

Purification: The Existential Dimension

Through Heidegger, the same absence can be read as *purification*. The body already goes unnoticed in everyday life; the digital medium *equalises this absence for everyone*. Freedom from the pressure of social performance, freedom from the prejudices created by physical appearance, and the possibility of attending to words alone.

Collision: The Dimension of Awareness

This analysis deepens the dimension of the collision. The problem is not simply “one person is transmitting information while the other is looking for social signals.” The problem is that two different *ways of being* meet on the same platform. One person experiences the digital medium as purification — freedom from body and appearance; the other experiences it as loss — the erasure of the face and the body. Both are consistent within their own experience — yet neither can see the other’s.

What is at stake is not different thinking styles — it is different *ways of existing*. And this difference means that two people can exist in fundamentally different worlds within the same messaging window, before the same words.

VII. What Takes the Place of the Face?

Digital communication eliminates Levinas’s face. Yet people continue to form ethical relationships in faceless spaces, to feel responsibility, to sense the other person’s fragility. How?

Emojis are a weak substitute for nonverbal cues (Aldunate & González-Ibáñez, 2017; Yuasa et al., 2006). But they serve another function: they carry *the trace of a body*. A smiley emoji reminds us that the person on the other side can laugh, grieve, break — that they *have* a body. A faint reminder, but not entirely without effect.

Profile photographs do something similar: they remind us that the other person has a face. But this is not Levinas's face — it is a photograph, a representation, a copy that stands in for the face without bearing the face's resistance. It is far easier to block someone while looking at their profile photo than to reject them while looking into their face.

Perhaps the closest thing to a face in the digital medium is *narrative*. When someone tells their own story — putting their pain, their fear, their hope, their vulnerability into words — the reader can encounter a kind of face. But this encounter is not automatic; the reader must *open* themselves to the narrative, must *think* of the person behind the words. Face to face, the face *imposes itself* — unless you close your eyes, it persists before you. On screen, narrative *invites* — you can read it, skip it, ignore it.

The transformation of the ethical encounter from imposition to invitation is the fundamental structural difference of the digital medium.

Conclusion

This essay does not propose a synthesis — because the three perspectives cannot be reduced to one another. For Levinas, the absence of the face is an ethical crisis. For Merleau-Ponty, the absence of the body is a perceptual rupture. For Heidegger, the absence of the body is the becoming-visible of something that was already the case. All three are true — but if all three are true at once, then digital communication is simultaneously a crisis, a rupture, and a discovery.

This multiplicity of meaning is no accident. The digital medium separates things that work together in face-to-face communication — the ethical encounter, bodily resonance, the sense of being there. Face to face, these are experienced as a whole; in the digital medium, each is separately *absent*, and each absence produces a different consequence.

Perhaps the deepest effect of digital communication is precisely this power of separation. It forces us to ask questions we never ask face to face: what is the face for? What is the body for? Is communication possible without them — and if so, is it something else?

Levinas's answer is clear: without the face, the ethical relation weakens. Merleau-Ponty's answer is different: without the body, perception changes but does not disappear. Heidegger's answer is the most radical: the body was never there at all.

And perhaps the real question is not which of these three answers is correct, but which one the person reading a message is living in at that moment. Because the same message may produce an ethical tremor in one person, a bodily longing in another, and no sense of anything missing in a third.

The true invisible void of digital communication may be this: that people who live the same absence differently never see each other's experience at all.

A note on this translation

This text was originally written in Turkish. We aimed for organic expression in each language – but small issues are inevitable. If you spot an error or a more natural phrasing, write to soru@halitcengizuzuner.com.

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